

IPBES IAS assessment, data management report for Chapter 1. Introduction

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Description

A systematic literature review was conducted as part of the Chapter 1 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive species and their control to find illustrative examples of IAS with ecological or socio-economic impact within terrestrial and aquatic environments spanning all the IPBES Units of Analysis around the world. A systematic review methodology was applied using Institute for Scientific Information Web of Science (ISI WOS) as search engine (<https://login.webofknowledge.com>; June 2020)

Process overview

Examples given were selected from the most cited papers. A systematic review methodology was applied using Institute for Scientific Information Web of Science (ISI WOS) as search engine (<https://login.webofknowledge.com>; June 2020). The keywords were considered in sequential filters: 1. IAS related (22 keywords); 2. Unit of analyses (keywords ranging from 2 to 3); and Mechanism of impact: environmental impact related (15 keywords) or socio-economical impact (26 keywords). All keywords were obtained through a participatory process (Chapter 1 CLA + fellows).

Protocol

- Type of analysis/search/review

Systematic review

- Search language(s)

English

- Search terms

See below

- Search engine

ISI WOS as search engine <https://login.webofknowledge.com>

- Date

June 2020

- List of reviewed literature

Articles for table with IAS examples.xlsx

- Overview of the search results and selection criteria

Illustrative examples of IAS within terrestrial and aquatic environments spanning all the IPBES Units of Analysis around the world.

Number in the table represent the number of the combination of the column and row name were searched.

Presented in red those searches without results

Presented in orange with an* all the searches performed with a different set of keywords (in this case just using "health")

Ecosystem	Unit of Analysis	Invasions, environment, ecosystem & environmental impacts	Invasions, environment, ecosystem & social impacts	Invasions, environment, ecosystem & responses measures	Invasions, environment, ecosystem & GQL	Invasions, environment, ecosystem & ILK	Invasions, environment, ecosystem & xenophobia
		[Search n°]	[Search n°]	[Search n°]	[Search n°]	[Search n°]	[Search n°]
Terrestrial	Tropical and subtropical dry and humid forests	1	2	3	4* (just using "health")	5	6
	Temperate and boreal forests and woodlands	7	8	9	10* (just using "health")	11	12
	Mediterranean forests, woodlands and scrub	13	14	15	16* (just using "health")	17	18
	Tundra and High Mountain habitats	19	20	21	22* (just using "health")	23	24
	Tropical and subtropical savannas and grasslands	25	26	27	28* (just using "health")	29	30
	Temperate Grasslands	31	32	33	34* (just using "health")	35	36
	Deserts and xeric shrublands	37	38	39	40* (just using "health")	41	42
	Wetlands – peatlands, mires, bogs	43	44	45	46* (just using "health")	47	48
	Urban/Semi-urban	49	50	51	52* (just using "health")	53	54
Cultivated areas (incl.	55	56	57	58* (just using	59	60	

	cropping, intensive livestock farming etc.)				"health")		
Aquatic (marine and freshwater)	Cryosphere	61	62	63	64* (just using "health")	65	66
	Aquaculture areas	67	68	69	70	71	72
	Inland surface waters and water bodies/freshwater	73	74	75	76	77	78
	Shelf ecosystems (neritic and intertidal/littoral zone)	79	80	81	82* (just using "health")	83	84
	Open ocean pelagic systems (euphotic zone)	85	86	87	88* (just using "health")	89	90
	Deep-Sea	91	92	93	94* (just using "health")	95	96
	Coastal areas intensively used for multiple purposes by humans	97	98	99	100* (just using "health")	101	102
Terrestrial (all ecosystems)				103	104	105	106
Aquatic (marine and freshwater) (all ecosystems)				107	108	109	110
Invasions (without environment or ecosystem specified)					111	112	113

Appendix

- Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.)

Search 1 – 96 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.1 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 210 records

("tropic* dry*" or "tropic* humid*" or "subtropic*" or "sub*tropic* dry*" or "subtropic* humid*" or "sub*tropic* humid*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 96 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation* " or "hybridization* " or "transmission of disease* " or "parasitism* " or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling " or "grazing*" or "herbivory " or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 2 – 103 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.1 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 210 records

("tropic* dry*" or "tropic* humid*" or "subtropic*" or "sub*tropic* dry*" or "subtropic* humid*" or "sub*tropic* humid*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 103 records

("Human* health* " or " well-being*" or " wellbeing*" or " liveabilit*" or " econom*" or " income*" or " propert* value*" or " culture*" or " heritage*" or " sacred space*" or " communit*" or " tension*" or " identit*" or " infrastructure* safety" or " people safety" or " propert* safety" or " disruption* " or " biosecurity" or " biosafety" or " bio*security" or " bio*safety" or " trad*" or " IUU fishing" or " ilegal wildlife " or " bioculture" or " bio*culture")

Search 3 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.1 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 210 records

("tropic* dry*" or "tropic* humid*" or "subtropic*" or "sub*tropic* dry*" or "subtropic* humid*" or "sub*tropic* humid*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – NO RESULTS

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 4 – 4 records* (using "health" in keyword 7)

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.1 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 210 records

("tropic* dry*" or "tropic* humid*" or "subtropic*" or "sub*tropic* dry*" or "subtropic* humid*" or "sub*tropic* humid*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 4 records** using:

("health*")

Search 5 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.1 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 210 records

("tropic* dry*" or "tropic* humid*" or "subtropic*" or "sub*tropic* dry*" or "subtropic* humid*" or "sub*tropic* humid*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – *NO RESULTS*

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 6 – *NO RESULTS*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.1 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 210 records

("tropic* dry*" or "tropic* humid*" or "subtropic*" or "sub*tropic* dry*" or "subtropic* humid*" or "sub*tropic* humid*")

Keyword 9 – *NO RESULTS*

("xenophobia*")

Search 7 – 669 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.2 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1,434 records

("temperat*" or "boreal*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 669 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation* " or "hybridization* " or "transmission of disease* " or "parasitism* " or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling " or "grazing*" or "herbivory " or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 8 – 669 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative

landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.2 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1,434 records

("temperat*" or "boreal*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 669 records

("Human* health* " or " well-being*" or " wellbeing*" or " liveabilit*" or " econom*" or " income*" or " propert* value*" or " culture*" or " heritage*" or " sacred space*" or " communit*" or " tension*" or " identit*" or " infrastructure* safety" or " people safety" or " propert* safety" or " disruption* " or " biosecurity" or " biosafety" or " bio*security" or " bio*safety" or " trad*" or " IUU fishing" or " ilegal wildlife " or " bioculture" or " bio*culture")

Search 9 – 9 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.2 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1,434 records

("temperat*" or "boreal*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 9 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 10 – 62 records* (using “health” in keyword 7)

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.2 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1,434 records

("temperat*" or "boreal*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 62 records** using:

("health*")

Search 11 – 1 record

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.2 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1,434 records

("temperat*" or "boreal*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – 1 record

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 12 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.2 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1,434 records

("temperat*" or "boreal*")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 13 – 204 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.3 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related - 422 records

("mediterran*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 204 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation* " or "hybridization* " or "transmission of disease* " or "parasitism* " or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling " or "grazing*" or "herbivory " or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 14 – 213 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.3 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related - 422 records

("mediterran*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 213 records

("Human* health* " or " well-being*" or " wellbeing*" or " liveabilit*" or " econom*" or " income*" or " propert* value*" or " culture*" or " heritage*" or " sacred space*" or " communit*" or " tension*" or " identit*" or " infrastructure* safety" or " people safety" or " propert* safety" or " disruption* " or " biosecurity" or " biosafety" or " bio*security" or " bio*safety" or " trad*" or " IUU fishing" or " ilegal wildlife " or " bioculture" or " bio*culture")

Search 15 – 3 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.3 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related - 422 records

("mediterran*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 3 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 16 – 13 records* (using “health” in keyword 7)

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.3 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related - 422 records

("mediterran*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 13 records** using:

("health*")

Search 17 NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.3 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related - 422 records

("mediterran*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – NO RESULTS

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 18 NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.3 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related - 422 records

("mediterran*")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 19 – 21 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.4 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 41 records

("tundr*" or "high mountain*" or "high-mountain*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 21 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation*" or "hybridization*" or "transmission of disease*" or "parasitism*" or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling" or "grazing*" or "herbivory" or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 20 – 27 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.4 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 41 records

("tundr*" or "high mountain*" or "high-mountain*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 27 records

("Human* health* " or " well-being*" or " wellbeing*" or " liveabilit*" or " econom*" or " income*" or " propert* value*" or " culture*" or " heritage*" or " sacred space*" or " communit*" or " tension*" or " identit*" or " infrastructure* safety" or " people safety" or " propert* safety" or " disruption* " or " biosecurity" or " biosafety" or " bio*security" or " bio*safety" or " trad*" or " IUU fishing" or " ilegal wildlife " or " bioculture" or " bio*culture")

Search 21 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.4 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 41 records

("tundr*" or "high mountain*" or "high-mountain*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – NO RESULTS

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 22 – 1 record*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.4 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 41 records

("tundr*" or "high mountain*" or "high-mountain*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 1 record** using:

("health*")

Search 23 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.4 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 41 records

("tundr*" or "high mountain*" or "high-mountain")

Keyword 8 ILK related – NO RESULTS

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 24 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.4 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 41 records

("tundr*" or "high mountain*" or "high-mountain")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 25 – 37 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.5 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related - 55 records

("tropic* savanna*" or "tropic* grassland*" or "subtropic* savanna*" or "sub*tropic* savanna*" or "subtropic* grassland*" or "sub*tropic* grassland*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 37 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation* " or "hybridization* " or "transmission of disease* " or "parasitism* " or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling " or "grazing*" or "herbivory " or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 26 – 29 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.5 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related - 55 records

("tropic* savanna*" or "tropic* grassland*" or "subtropic* savanna*" or "sub*tropic* savanna*" or "subtropic* grassland*" or "sub*tropic* grassland*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 29 records

("Human* health* " or " well-being*" or " wellbeing*" or " liveabilit*" or " econom*" or " income*" or " propert* value*" or " culture*" or " heritage*" or " sacred space*" or " communit*" or " tension*" or " identit*" or " infrastructure* safety" or " people safety" or " propert* safety" or " disruption* " or " biosecurity" or " biosafety" or " bio*security" or " bio*safety" or " trad*" or " IUU fishing" or " ilegal wildlife " or " bioculture" or " bio*culture")

Search 27 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.5 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related - 55 records

("tropic* savanna*" or "tropic* grassland*" or "subtropic* savanna*" or "sub*tropic* savanna*" or "subtropic* grassland*" or "sub*tropic* grassland*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – NO RESULTS

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 28 – 1 record*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.5 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related - 55 records

("tropic* savanna*" or "tropic* grassland*" or "subtropic* savanna*" or "sub*tropic* savanna*" or "subtropic* grassland*" or "sub*tropic* grassland*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 1 record** using:

("health*")

Search 29 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.5 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related - 55 records

("tropic* savanna*" or "tropic* grassland*" or "subtropic* savanna*" or "sub*tropic* savanna*" or "subtropic* grassland*" or "sub*tropic* grassland*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – NO RESULTS

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 30 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.5 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related - 55 records

("tropic* savanna*" or "tropic* grassland*" or "subtropic* savanna*" or "sub*tropic* savanna*" or "subtropic* grassland*" or "sub*tropic* grassland*")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 31 – 639 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.6 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1,182 records

("grassland*" or "steppe*" or "pampa*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 639 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation* " or "hybridization* " or "transmission of disease* " or "parasitism* " or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling " or "grazing*" or "herbivory " or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 32 – 743 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.6 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1,182 records

("grassland*" or "steppe*" or "pampa*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 743 records

("Human* health* " or " well-being*" or " wellbeing*" or " liveabilit*" or " econom*" or " income*" or " propert* value*" or " culture*" or " heritage*" or " sacred space*" or " communit*" or " tension*" or " identit*" or " infrastructure* safety" or " people safety" or " propert* safety" or " disruption* " or " biosecurity" or " biosafety" or " bio*security" or " bio*safety" or " trad*" or " IUU fishing" or " ilegal wildlife " or " bioculture" or " bio*culture")

Search 33 – 7 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.6 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1,182 records

("grassland*" or "steppe*" or "pampa*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 7 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 34 – 30 records*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative

landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.6 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1,182 records

("grassland*" or "steppe*" or "pampa*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 30 records** using:

("health*")

Search 35 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.6 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1,182 records

("grassland*" or "steppe*" or "pampa*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – NO RESULTS

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 36 – 1 record

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.6 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1,182 records

("grassland*" or "steppe*" or "pampa*")

Keyword 9 – 1 record

("xenophobia*")

Search 37 – 208 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.7 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 393 records

("desert*" or "xeric*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 208 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation*" or "hybridization*" or "transmission of disease*" or "parasitism*" or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling" or "grazing*" or "herbivory" or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 38 – 193 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.7 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 393 records

("desert*" or "xeric*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 193 records

("Human* health*" or "well-being*" or "wellbeing*" or "liveabilit*" or "econom*" or "income*" or "propert* value*" or "culture*" or "heritage*" or "sacred space*" or "communit*" or "tension*" or "identit*" or "infrastructure* safety" or "people safety" or "propert* safety" or "disruption*" or "

biosecurity" or " biosafety" or " bio*security" or " bio*safety" or " trad*" or " IUU fishing" or " ilegal wildlife " or " bioculture" or " bio*culture")

Search 39 – 4 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.7 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 393 records

("desert*" or "xeric*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 4 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 40 – 6 records*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.7 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 393 records

("desert*" or "xeric*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 6 records** using:

("health*")

Search 41 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.7 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 393 records

("desert*" or "xeric*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – NO RESULTS

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 42 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.7 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 393 records

("desert*" or "xeric*")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 43 – 347 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.8 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 748 records

("wetland*" or "peatland*" or "mire*" or "bog*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 347 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation*" or "hybridization*" or "transmission of disease*" or "parasitism*" or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling" or "grazing*" or "herbivory" or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 44 – 408 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.8 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 748 records

("wetland*" or "peatland*" or "mire*" or "bog*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 408 records

("Human* health*" or "well-being*" or "wellbeing*" or "liveabilit*" or "econom*" or "income*" or "propert* value*" or "culture*" or "heritage*" or "sacred space*" or "communit*" or "tension*" or "identit*" or "infrastructure* safety" or "people safety" or "propert* safety" or "disruption*" or "biosecurity" or "biosafety" or "bio*security" or "bio*safety" or "trad*" or "IUU fishing" or "ilegal wildlife" or "bioculture" or "bio*culture")

Search 45 – 10 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.8 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 748 records

("wetland*" or "peatland*" or "mire*" or "bog*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 10 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 46 – 29 records*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.8 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 748 records

("wetland*" or "peatland*" or "mire*" or "bog*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 29 records** using:

("health*")

Search 47 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.8 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 748 records

("wetland*" or "peatland*" or "mire*" or "bog*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – NO RESULTS

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 48 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.8 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 748 records

("wetland*" or "peatland*" or "mire*" or "bog*")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 49 – 587 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.9 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1404 records

("urban*" or "semi-urban*" or "semiurban*" or "semi*urban*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 587 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation*" or "hybridization*" or "transmission of disease*" or "parasitism*" or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling" or "grazing*" or "herbivory" or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 50 – 747 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.9 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1404 records

("urban*" or "semi-urban*" or "semiurban*" or "semi*urban*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 747 records

("Human* health*" or "well-being*" or "wellbeing*" or "liveabilit*" or "econom*" or "income*" or "propert* value*" or "culture*" or "heritage*" or "sacred space*" or "communit*" or "tension*" or "identit*" or "infrastructure* safety" or "people safety" or "propert* safety" or "disruption*" or "biosecurity" or "biosafety" or "bio*security" or "bio*safety" or "trad*" or "IUU fishing" or "ilegal wildlife" or "bioculture" or "bio*culture")

Search 51 – 40 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.9 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1404 records

("urban*" or "semi-urban*" or "semiurban*" or "semi*urban*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 40 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 52 – 107 records*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.9 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1404 records

("urban*" or "semi-urban*" or "semiurban*" or "semi*urban*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 107 records** using:

("health*")

Search 53 – 2 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.9 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1404 records

("urban*" or "semi-urban*" or "semiurban*" or "semi*urban*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – 2 records

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 54 – 1 record

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or

"introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.9 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1404 records

("urban*" or "semi-urban*" or "semiurban*" or "semi*urban*")

Keyword 9 – 1 record

("xenophobia*")

Search 55 – 834 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.10 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1743 records

("cultiv*" or "crop*" or "livestock*" or "farm*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 834 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation*" or "hybridization*" or "transmission of disease*" or "parasitism*" or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling" or "grazing*" or "herbivory" or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 56 – 905 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.10 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1743 records

("cultiv*" or "crop*" or "livestock*" or "farm*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 905 records

("Human* health*" or "well-being*" or "wellbeing*" or "liveabilit*" or "econom*" or "income*" or "propert* value*" or "culture*" or "heritage*" or "sacred space*" or "communit*" or "tension*" or "identit*" or "infrastructure* safety" or "people safety" or "propert* safety" or "disruption*" or "biosecurity" or "biosafety" or "bio*security" or "bio*safety" or "trad*" or "IUU fishing" or "illegal wildlife" or "bioculture" or "bio*culture")

Search 57 – 33 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or

"introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.10 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1743 records

("cultiv*" or "crop*" or "livestock*" or "farm*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 33 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 58 – 103 records*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.10 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1743 records

("cultiv*" or "crop*" or "livestock*" or "farm*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 103 GQL – records** using:

("health*")

Search 59 – 4 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.10 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1743 records

("cultiv*" or "crop*" or "livestock*" or "farm*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – 4 records

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 60 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 3.10 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 1743 records

("cultiv*" or "crop*" or "livestock*" or "farm*")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 61 – 51 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.11 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 104 records

("cryosphere*" or "ice" or "frozen" or "permafrost")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 51 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation*" or "hybridization*" or "transmission of disease*" or "parasitism*" or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling" or "grazing*" or "herbivory" or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 62 – 51 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.11 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 104 records

("cryosphere*" or "ice" or "frozen" or "permafrost")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 51 records

("Human* health*" or "well-being*" or "wellbeing*" or "liveabilit*" or "econom*" or "income*" or "propert* value*" or "culture*" or "heritage*" or "sacred space*" or "communit*" or "tension*" or "identit*" or "infrastructure* safety" or "people safety" or "propert* safety" or "disruption*" or "biosecurity" or "biosafety" or "bio*security" or "bio*safety" or "trad*" or "IUU fishing" or "ilegal wildlife" or "bioculture" or "bio*culture")

Search 63 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.11 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 104 records

("cryosphere*" or "ice" or "frozen" or "permafrost")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – NO RESULTS

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 64 – 5 records*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.11 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 104 records

("cryosphere*" or "ice" or "frozen" or "permafrost")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 5 records** using:

("health*")

Search 65 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.11 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 104 records

("cryosphere*" or "ice" or "frozen" or "permafrost")

Keyword 8 ILK related – NO RESULTS

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 66 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.11 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 104 records

("cryosphere*" or "ice" or "frozen" or "permafrost")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 67 – 321 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.12 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 664 records

("aquaculture*" or "aqua*culture")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 321 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation*" or "hybridization*" or "transmission of disease*" or "parasitism*" or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling" or "grazing*" or "herbivory" or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 68 – 418 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.12 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 664 records

("aquaculture*" or "aqua*culture")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 418 records

("Human* health*" or "well-being*" or "wellbeing*" or "liveabilit*" or "econom*" or "income*" or "propert* value*" or "culture*" or "heritage*" or "sacred space*" or "communit*" or "tension*" or "identit*" or "infrastructure* safety" or "people safety" or "propert* safety" or "disruption*" or "biosecurity" or "biosafety" or "bio*security" or "bio*safety" or "trad*" or "IUU fishing" or "ilegal wildlife" or "bioculture" or "bio*culture")

Search 69 – 9 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.12 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 664 records

("aquaculture*" or "aqua*culture")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 9 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 70 – 1 record

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.12 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 664 records

("aquaculture*" or "aqua*culture")

Keyword 7 GQL related – 1 records

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

Search 71 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.12 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 664 records

("aquaculture*" or "aqua*culture")

Keyword 8 ILK related – NO RESULTS

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 72 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.12 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 664 records

("aquaculture*" or "aqua*culture")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 73 – 2090 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.13 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 4,217 records

("surface water*" or "water*bodies" or "waterbodies" or "water*body" or "waterbody" or "freshwater*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 2090 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation*" or "hybridization*" or "transmission of disease*" or "parasitism*" or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling " or "grazing*" or "herbivory " or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 74 – 1,869 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.13 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 4,217 records

("surface water*" or "water*bodies" or "waterbodies" or "water*body" or "waterbody" or "freshwater*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 1,869 records

("Human* health* " or " well-being*" or " wellbeing*" or " liveabilit*" or " econom*" or " income*" or " propert* value*" or " culture*" or " heritage*" or " sacred space*" or " communit*" or " tension*" or " identit*" or " infrastructure* safety" or " people safety" or " propert* safety" or " disruption* " or " biosecurity" or " biosafety" or " bio*security" or " bio*safety" or " trad*" or " IUU fishing" or " ilegal wildlife " or " bioculture" or " bio*culture")

Search 75 – 22 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.13 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 4,217 records

("surface water*" or "water*bodies" or "waterbodies" or "water*body" or "waterbody" or "freshwater*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 22 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 76 – 1 record

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.13 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 4,217 records

("surface water*" or "water*bodies" or "waterbodies" or "water*body" or "waterbody" or "freshwater*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – 1 record

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

Search 77 – 3 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.13 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 4,217 records

("surface water*" or "water*bodies" or "waterbodies" or "water*body" or "waterbody" or "freshwater*")

Keyword ILK related – 3 records

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 78 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.13 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 4,217 records

("surface water*" or "water*bodies" or "waterbodies" or "water*body" or "waterbody" or "freshwater*")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 79 – 385 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.14 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 746 records

("shelf*" or "neritic*" or "intertidal*" or "littoral*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 385 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation*" or "hybridization*" or "transmission of disease*" or "parasitism*" or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling" or "grazing*" or "herbivory" or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 80 – 451 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.14 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 746 records

("shelf*" or "neritic*" or "intertidal*" or "littoral*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 451 records

("Human* health*" or "well-being*" or "wellbeing*" or "liveabilit*" or "econom*" or "income*" or "propert* value*" or "culture*" or "heritage*" or "sacred space*" or "communit*" or "tension*" or "identit*" or "infrastructure* safety" or "people safety" or "propert* safety" or "disruption*" or "biosecurity" or "biosafety" or "bio*security" or "bio*safety" or "trad*" or "IUU fishing" or "ilegal wildlife" or "bioculture" or "bio*culture")

Search 81 – 3 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.14 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 746 records

("shelf*" or "neritic*" or "intertidal*" or "littoral*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 3 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 82 – 18 records*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.14 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 746 records

("shelf*" or "neritic*" or "intertidal*" or "littoral*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 18 records** using:

("health*")

Search 83 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.14 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 746 records

("shelf*" or "neritic*" or "intertidal*" or "littoral*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – NO RESULTS

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 84 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.14 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 746 records

("shelf*" or "neritic*" or "intertidal*" or "littoral*")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 85 – 120 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.15 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 256 records

("open ocean pelagic*" or "ocean pelagic*" or "pelagic*" or "euphotic*")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 120 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation*" or "hybridization*" or "transmission of disease*" or "parasitism*" or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling " or "grazing*" or "herbivory " or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 86 – 140 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.15 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 256 records

("open ocean pelagic*" or "ocean pelagic*" or "pelagic*" or "euphotic*")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 140 records

("Human* health* " or " well-being*" or " wellbeing*" or " liveabilit*" or " econom*" or " income*" or " propert* value*" or " culture*" or " heritage*" or " sacred space*" or " communit*" or " tension*" or " identit*" or " infrastructure* safety" or " people safety" or " propert* safety" or " disruption* " or " biosecurity" or " biosafety" or " bio*security" or " bio*safety" or " trad*" or " IUU fishing" or " ilegal wildlife " or " bioculture" or " bio*culture")

Search 87 – 2 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.15 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 256 records

("open ocean pelagic*" or "ocean pelagic*" or "pelagic*" or "euphotic*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 2 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 88 – 4 records*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.15 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 256 records

("open ocean pelagic*" or "ocean pelagic*" or "pelagic*" or "euphotic*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 4 records** using:

("health*")

Search 89 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.15 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 256 records

("open ocean pelagic*" or "ocean pelagic*" or "pelagic*" or "euphotic*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – NO RESULTS

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 90 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.15 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 256 records

("open ocean pelagic*" or "ocean pelagic*" or "pelagic*" or "euphotic*")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 91 – 13 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.16 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 43 records

("deep-sea" or "deepsea" or "deep sea")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 13 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation*" or "hybridization*" or "transmission of disease*" or "parasitism*" or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling " or "grazing*" or "herbivory " or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 92 – 26 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.16 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 43 records

("deep-sea" or "deepsea" or "deep sea")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 26 records

("Human* health* " or " well-being*" or " wellbeing*" or " liveabilit*" or " econom*" or " income*" or " propert* value*" or " culture*" or " heritage*" or " sacred space*" or " communit*" or " tension*" or " identit*" or " infrastructure* safety" or " people safety" or " propert* safety" or " disruption* " or " biosecurity" or " biosafety" or " bio*security" or " bio*safety" or " trad*" or " IUU fishing" or " ilegal wildlife " or " bioculture" or " bio*culture")

Search 93 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.16 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 43 records

("deep-sea" or "deepsea" or "deep sea")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – NO RESULTS

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 94 – 2 records*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.16 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 43 records

("deep-sea" or "deepsea" or "deep sea")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 2 records** using:

("health*")

Search 95 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.16 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 43 records

("deep-sea" or "deepsea" or "deep sea")

Keyword 8 ILK related – NO RESULTS

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 96 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.16 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 43 records

("deep-sea" or "deepsea" or "deep sea")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 97 – 1088 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.17 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 2446 records

("coast*" or "human use*" or "human-use")

Keyword 4 Environmental Impacts related – 1088 records

("impact*" or "competition*" or "predation*" or "hybridisation*" or "hybridization*" or "transmission of disease*" or "parasitism*" or "poisoning" or "toxicit*" or "bio*fouling" or "grazing*" or "herbivory" or "browsing" or "impact* on ecosystem*")

Search 98 – 1238 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.17 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 2446 records

("coast*" or "human use*" or "human-use")

Keyword 5 Social impacts related – 1238 records

("Human* health*" or "well-being*" or "wellbeing*" or "liveabilit*" or "econom*" or "income*" or "propert* value*" or "culture*" or "heritage*" or "sacred space*" or "communit*" or "tension*" or "identit*" or "infrastructure* safety" or "people safety" or "propert* safety" or "disruption*" or "biosecurity" or "biosafety" or "bio*security" or "bio*safety" or "trad*" or "IUU fishing" or "illegal wildlife" or "bioculture" or "bio*culture")

Search 99 – 34 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.17 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 2446 records

("coast*" or "human use*" or "human-use")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 34 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 100 – 109 records*

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.17 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 2446 records

("coast*" or "human use*" or "human-use")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

***Adapted keyword 7 GQL – 109 records** using:

("health*")

Search 101 – 1 record

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.17 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 2446 records

("coast*" or "human use*" or "human-use")

Keyword 8 ILK related – 1 record

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 102 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 3.17 Ecosystem / unit of analysis related – 2446 records

("coast*" or "human use*" or "human-use")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Extra searches to disentangle the role of *responses measures; GQL; ILK and xenophobia* in the literature

Search 103 – 176 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 176 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 104 – NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – NO RESULTS

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

Search 105 – 13 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – 13 records

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 106 – 4 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.1 Environmental related - 13,735 records

("terrestr*" or "land*")

Keyword 9 – 4 records

("xenophobia*")

Search 107 – 111 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 6 Impact of responses measures related – 111 records

("legitimacy" or "participati*" or "citizen science")

Search 108 – 3 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 7 GQL related – 3 records

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

Search 109 – 5 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 8 ILK related – 5 record

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 110 NO RESULTS

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 2.2 Environmental related - 12,850 records

("freshwater*" or "marin*" or "aquatic*")

Keyword 9 – NO RESULTS

("xenophobia*")

Search 111 – 15 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 7 GQL related – 15 records

("One Health approach" or "Health approach*")

Search 112 – 131 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 8 ILK related – 131 record

("ILK" or "traditional knowledge")

Search 113- 12 records

Keyword 1 Invasion related - 457,275 records

("ecological invasion*" or "biological invasion*" or "invasion* biology" or "invasion* ecology" or "invasive species" or "alien species" or "nonnative species" or "non-native species" or "nonindigenous species" or "non-indigenous species" or "allochthonous species" or "exotic species" or "invader*" or "introduced species" or "invasive*" or "introduced landscape" or "non-native landscape" or "nonnative landscape" or "nonindigenous landscape" or "non-indigenous landscape" or "allochthonous landscape" or "novel ecosystem")

Keyword 9 – 12 records

("xenophobia*")